

Analysis of testing approaches to Android mobile application vulnerabilities

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Abstract. In the first part of the article we discuss international, industrial and national standards and methodologies that describe the process of testing for application vulnerabilities, including mobile applications for Android OS. The following standards and methodologies were taken for the study: ISO/IEC 27034. Information technology. Security techniques. Application Security, NIST 800-163 Vetting the Security of Mobile application, National Information Assurance Partnership and Mobile application security verification standard. Also, we have compared methods it selves and methods of testing for vulnerabilities of mobile software applications for operating system Android. The analysis of the stages by which testing for vulnerabilities is carried out. The second part of the article presents statistics on vulnerabilities that were published by vendors – Google security statistics and Quick Heal, as well as statistics, which were formed by the authors of the publication. For statistics, the test results were taken from an online store, two crypto exchanges and two crypto wallets. The conclusions to the article summarize the results of a study of standards and statistics for conducting subsequent research on the subject of scientific work.

Keywords: mobile application, security assessment, security testing, Open Web Application Security Project, ISO/IEC 27034, National Information Assurance Partnership.

1 Introduction

According to Beta News, among the 30 best applications with more than 500,000 downloads, 94% contain at least 3 average risk vulnerabilities, while 77% contain at minimum two high-level vulnerabilities. Among the 30 applications 17% were vulnerable to Man-In-The-Middle (MITM) attacks exposing all data to interception by malicious users. Furthermore, 44% of applications contain confidential data with strict encryption requirements, including passwords or Application Programming Interface (API) keys, while 66% utilize functional abilities which can compromise users' confidentiality. This is exactly why mobile devices are subject to numerous security discussions [1].

2 Application security standards

2.1 ISO/IEC 27034. Information technology. Security techniques. Application Security

ISO/IEC 27034 offers guidance on information security to those specifying, designing and programming or procuring, implementing and using application systems, in other words business and Information Technology (IT) managers, developers and auditors, and ultimately the end-users of Information and Communication Technology (ICT). The aim is to ensure that computer applications deliver the desired or necessary level of security in support of the organization's Information Security Management System, adequately addressing many ICT security risks.

This multi-part standard provides guidance on specifying, designing/selecting and implementing information security controls through a set of processes integrated throughout an organization's Systems Development Life Cycle (SDLC). It is process oriented [2] - [5].

It covers software applications developed internally, by external acquisition, outsourcing/offshoring or through hybrid approaches. It addresses all aspects from determining information security requirements, to protecting information accessed by an application as well as preventing unauthorized use and/or actions of an application. The standard is SDLC-method-agnostic: it does not mandate one or more specific development methods, approaches or stages but is written in a general manner to be applicable to them all. In this way, it complements other systems development standards and methods without conflicting with them. One of the key driving principles is that it is worth investing more heavily in specifying, designing, developing and testing software security controls or functions if they are reusable across multiple applications, systems and situations, albeit at the risk of propagating vulnerabilities more widely than might otherwise be the case. In a nutshell, "Do it properly, do it once, and reuse it". The approach may seem a little idealistic, but some far-sighted organizations are already successfully using it: it is more than just an academic interest [3] - [6].

Section 8.5 "Security Audit" of this standard consists of verification and formal confirmation of evidence that the application that is being developed is at the required level of security, which is written in the technical documentation. An application security audit can be performed at any time during the development and operation life cycle. The sixth part of the standard ISO / IEC 27034-6:2016. Information technology. Security techniques. Application security. Part 6. Case studies does not describe how and by what means it is necessary to conduct testing. It shows just what needs to be tested [7], [8].

2.2 NIST 800-163 Vetting the Security of Mobile application

This document defines an app vetting process and provides guidance on planning and implementing an app vetting process, developing security requirements for mobile apps, identifying appropriate tools for testing mobile apps and determining if a mobile app is acceptable for deployment on an organization's mobile devices. An overview of

techniques commonly used by software assurance professionals is provided, including methods of testing for discrete software vulnerabilities and misconfigurations related to mobile app software [9], [10].

Standards includes security checks according to which mobile applications are tested [10]:

1.2.1 Incorrect Permissions. Permissions allow accessing controlled functionality such as the camera or Global Positioning System (GPS) and are requested in the program. Permissions can be implicitly granted to an app without the user's consent.

1.2.2 Exposed Communications. Internal communications protocols are the means by which an app passes messages internally within the device, either to itself or to other apps. External communications allow information to leave the device.

1.2.3 Exposed Data Storage. Files created by apps on Android can be stored in Internal Storage, External Storage, or the Keystore. Files stored in External Storage may be read and modified by all other apps with the External Storage permission.

1.2.4 Potentially Dangerous Functionality. Controlled functionality that accesses system-critical resources or the user's personal information. This functionality can be invoked through API calls or hard coded into an app.

1.2.5 App Collusion. Two or more apps passing information to each other in order to increase the capabilities of one or both apps beyond their declared scope.

1.2.6. Obfuscation. Functionality or control flows that are hidden or obscured from the user. For the purposes of this appendix, obfuscation was defined as three criteria: external library calls, reflection, and native code usage.

1.2.7. Excessive Power Consumption. Excessive functions or unintended apps running on a device which intentionally or unintentionally drain the battery.

1.2.8. Traditional Software Vulnerabilities. All vulnerabilities associated with traditional Java code including: Authentication and Access Control, Buffer Handling, Control Flow Management, Encryption and Randomness, Error Handling, File Handling, Information Leaks, Initialization and Shutdown, Injection, Malicious Logic, Number Handling, and Pointer and Reference Handling [2] - [7], [10].

2.3 National Information Assurance Partnership (NIAP)

This document presents functional and assurance requirements found in the Protection Profile for Application Software which are appropriate for vetting mobile application software ("apps") outside formal Common Criteria (ISO/IEC 15408) evaluations. Common Criteria evaluation, facilitated in the U.S. by the National Information Assurance Partnership (NIAP), is required for IA and IA-enabled products in National Security Systems according to Committee on National Security Systems (CNSS) Policy #11. Such evaluations, including those for mobile apps, must use the complete Protection Profile. However, even apps without IA functionality may impose some security risks, and concern about these risks has motivated the vetting of such apps in government and industry [2].

Security Functional Requirements [3]:

1.3.1. Random Bit Generation Services. If implement Deterministic Random Bit Generator (DRBG) functionality is chosen, then additional security requirements elements shall be included in the ST. In this requirement, cryptographic operations include all cryptographic key generation/derivation/agreement, Initial Vector's (IVs) (for certain modes), as well as protocol-specific random values.

1.3.2. Storage of Credentials. This requirement ensures that persistent credentials (secret keys, Public Key Infrastructure (PKI) private keys, or passwords) are stored securely. The assurance activity implicitly restricts which selections can be made, on per-platform basis. For example, if a platform provides hardware-backed protection for credential storage, then the third selection cannot be indicated. If implement functionality to securely store credentials is selected, then the following components must be included in the Security Target (ST). If other cryptographic operations are used to implement the secure storage of credentials, the corresponding requirements must be included in the Security Target.

1.3.3. Access to Platform Resources. The intent is for the evaluator to ensure that the selection captures all hardware resources which the application accesses, and that these are restricted to those which are justified. On some platforms, the application must explicitly solicit permission in order to access hardware resources. Seeking such permissions, even if the application does not later make use of the hardware resource, should still be considered access. Selections should be expressed in a manner consistent with how the application expresses its access needs to the underlying platform. For example, the platform may provide location services which implies the potential use of a variety of hardware resources (e.g. satellite receivers, WiFi, cellular radio) yet location services are the proper selection. This is because use of these resources can be inferred, but also because the actual usage may vary based on the particular platform. Resources that do not need to be explicitly identified are those which are ordinarily used by any application such as central processing units, main memory, displays, input devices (e.g. keyboards, mice), and persistent storage devices provided by the platform. Sensitive information repositories are defined as those collections of sensitive data that could be expected to be shared among some applications, users, or user roles, but to which not all of these would ordinarily require access.

1.3.4. Network Communications. This requirement is intended to restrict both inbound and outbound network communications to only those required, or to network communications that are user initiated. It does not apply to network communications in which the application may generically access the filesystem which may result in the platform accessing remotely mounted drives/shares.

1.3.5. Encryption of Sensitive Application Data. Any file that may potentially contain sensitive data (to include temporary files) shall be protected. The only exception is if the user intentionally exports the sensitive data to non-protected files.

1.3.6. Supported Configuration Mechanism. Configuration options that are stored remotely are not subject to this requirement.

1.3.7. Secure by Default Configuration. Default credentials are credentials (e.g., passwords, keys) that are automatically (without user interaction) loaded onto the platform during application installation. Credentials that are generated during installation using requirements laid out in ST are not by definition default credentials. The precise

expectations for file permissions vary per platform but the general intention is that a trust boundary protects the application and its data.

1.3.8. Specification of Management Functions. This requirement stipulates that an application needs to provide the ability to enable/disable only those functions that it actually implements. The application is not responsible for controlling the behavior of the platform or other applications.

1.3.9. User Consent for Transmission of Personally Identifiable Information (PII). This requirement applies only to PII that is specifically requested by the application; it does not apply if the user volunteers PII without prompting from the application into a general (or inappropriate) data field. A dialog box that declares intent to send PII presented to the user at the time the application is started is sufficient to meet this requirement.

1.3.10. Use of Supported Services and APIs. The definition of documented may vary depending upon whether the application is provided by a third party (who relies upon documented platform APIs) or by a platform vendor who may be able to guarantee support for platform APIs.

1.3.11. Anti-Exploitation Capabilities. Requesting a memory mapping at an explicit address subverts address space layout randomization (ASLR). Requesting a memory mapping with both write and execute permissions subverts the platform protection provided by Data Execution Prevention (DEP). If the application performs no just-in-time compiling, then the first selection must be chosen.

1.3.12. Integrity for Installation and Update. This requirement is about the ability to “check” for updates. The actual installation of any updates should be done by the platform. This requirement is intended to ensure that the application can check for updates provided by the vendor, as updates provided by another source may contain malicious code.

1.3.13. Use of Third-Party Libraries. The intention of this requirement is for the evaluator to discover and document whether the application is including unnecessary or unexpected third-party libraries. This includes adware libraries which could present a privacy threat, as well as ensuring documentation of such libraries in case vulnerabilities are later discovered.

1.3.14. Protection of Data in Transit. Application should transmit sensitive data only via encryption channel.

2.4 Mobile application security verification standard (MASVS).

The MASVS is a community effort to establish a framework of security requirements needed to design, develop and test secure mobile apps on iOS and Android [4].

MASVS contains three parts (see Fig. 1):

Fig. 1. MASVS Systems

The Mobile Application Security Verification Standard (MASVS): This standard document defines a mobile app security model and lists generic security requirements for mobile apps. It can be used by architects, developers, testers, security professionals, and consumers to define what a secure mobile application is [4]. Check controls:

- V1: Architecture, Design and Threat Modeling Requirements.
- V2: Data Storage and Privacy Requirements.
- V3: Cryptography Requirements.
- V4: Authentication and Session Management Requirements.
- V5: Network Communication Requirements.
- V6: Platform Interaction Requirements.
- V7: Code Quality and Build Setting Requirements.
- V8: Resilience Requirements.

The Mobile Security Testing Guide (MSTG): The MSTG is a manual for testing the security of mobile apps. It provides verification instructions for the requirements in the MASVS along with operating-system-specific best practices (currently for Android and iOS). The MSTG helps ensure completeness and consistency of mobile app security test. It is also useful as a standalone learning resource and reference guide for mobile application security testers [4], [5].

Mobile App Security Checklist: A checklist for tracking compliance against the MASVS during practical assessments. The list conveniently links to the MSTG test case for each requirement, making mobile penetration app testing a breeze [4].

The MASVS defines two security verification levels (MASVS-L1 and MASVS-L2), as well as a set of reverse engineering resiliency requirements (MASVS-R). MASVS-L1 contains generic security requirements that are recommended for all mobile apps, while MASVS-L2 should be applied to apps handling highly sensitive data. MASVS-R covers additional protective controls that can be applied if preventing client-side threats is a design goal (see Fig. 2).

Fulfilling the requirements in MASVS-L1 results in a secure app that follows security best practices and doesn't suffer from common vulnerabilities. MASVS-L2 adds additional defense-in-depth controls such as SSL pinning, resulting in an app that is resilient against more sophisticated attacks - assuming the security controls of the mobile operating system are intact, and the end user is not viewed as a potential adversary. Fulfilling all, or subsets of, the software protection requirements in MASVS-R helps impede specific client-side threats where the end user is malicious and/or the mobile OS is compromised [4].

Fig. 2. MASVS security level [3], [4]

1.4.1. MASVS-L1: Standard Security. A mobile app that achieves MASVS-L1 adheres to mobile application security best practices. It fulfills basic requirements in terms of code quality, handling of sensitive data, and interaction with the mobile environment. A testing process must be in place to verify the security controls. This level is appropriate for all mobile applications [4].

1.4.2. MASVS-L2: Defense-in-Depth. MASVS-L2 introduces advanced security controls that go beyond the standard requirements. To fulfill MASVS-L2, a threat model must exist, and security must be an integral part of the app's architecture and design. Based on the threat model, the right MASVS-L2 controls should have been selected and implemented successfully. This level is appropriate for apps that handle highly sensitive data, such as mobile banking apps [4].

1.4.3. MASVS-R: Resiliency Against Reverse Engineering and Tampering. The app has state-of-the-art security, and is also resilient against specific, clearly defined client-side attacks, such as tampering, modding, or reverse engineering to extract sensitive code or data. Such an app either leverages hardware security features or sufficiently strong and verifiable software protection techniques. MASVS-R is applicable to apps that handle highly sensitive data and may serve as a means of protecting intellectual property or tamper-proofing an app [4].

Notes:

I: Although OWASP recommend implementing MASVS-L1 controls in every app, implementing a control or not should ultimately be a risk-based decision, which is taken/communicated with the business owners.

II: Note that the software protection controls listed in MASVS-R and described in the OWASP Mobile Security Testing Guide can ultimately be bypassed and must never be used as a replacement for security controls. Instead, they are intended to add additional threat-specific, protective controls to apps that also fulfill the MASVS requirements in MASVS-L1 or MASVS-L2 [4] - [6].

3 Statistics

3.1 Us perform testing statistics

Us personal statistics of vulnerability assessment Android mobile application (see Tabl. 1 – 5). We perform 5 tests on real mobile application and use MASVS for describe vulnerabilities [4] - [6].

Table 1. Cryptocurrency exchanger 1

High level vulnerabilities	Medium level vulnerabilities	Low level vulnerabilities	Information level vulnerabilities
Sensitive data in logs	SMS spam	Session fixation	Application uses old library
Brakforce password	Mobile phone number enumeration	SSL certificate potential vulnerable	Cross-origin resource sharing
	OTP return in response	No Certificate and Public Key Pinning	Vulnerability in old version of WebView
	Absence of source code obfuscation	Application data can be backup	

Table 2. Cryptocurrency exchanger 2

High level vulnerabilities	Medium level vulnerabilities	Low level vulnerabilities	Information level vulnerabilities
		No Certificate and Public Key Pinning	Application can run on rooting application
		SSL certificate potential vulnerable	
		Application can be backup	

Table 3. Cryptocurrency wallet 1

High level vulnerabilities	Medium level vulnerabilities	Low level vulnerabilities	Information level vulnerabilities
Sensitive data in logs	Absence of source code obfuscation	Backup private key explicitly visible	Application uses old library
Sensitive data saves in local files		Insecure communication – application uses HTTP	
		No Certificate and Public Key Pinning	

Table 4. Cryptocurrency wallet 2

High level vulnerabilities	Medium level vulnerabilities	Low level vulnerabilities	Information level vulnerabilities
Root and developer mode bypass	Absence of source code obfuscation	Application data can be backup	Vulnerability in old version of WebView
Critical bug in money transfer	Check modify source code	No Certificate and Public Key Pinning	
Personal data in logs	User Enumeration		

Table 5. Mobile marketplace

High level vulnerabilities	Medium level vulnerabilities	Low level vulnerabilities	Information level vulnerabilities
Two vulnerabilities – OTP value return in response	Absence of source code obfuscation	Unrestricted user creation	
Four vulnerabilities – Insecure direct object	Cleartext password submission	No Certificate and Public Key Pinning	
	User's info enumeration	Password changed attack	

3.2 Google security statistics

In 2018, 0.04% of all downloads from Google Play were Potentially Harmful Applications (PHAs). In 2017, the number was 0.02%. This increase is due to the change in methodology of upgrading the severity level of click fraud applications from policy violations to PHAs. If we omit the addition of click fraud for a comparison, 2018 is at 0.017% which is still a reduction from 2017 (see Fig. 3). Now we look for click fraud inside and outside of Google Play and warn users about these apps. All other PHA categories have declined each year or increased at low levels [11].

Fig. 3. Google security statistics

3.3 Quick Heal

Quick Heal Annual Threat Report 2019 brings forth insights and intelligence gathered by Quick Heal Security Labs about all that unfolded in the realm of cybersecurity in 2018 – divided into two sections viz (see Fig. 4). Windows and Android. The threat report begins with significant cyber-attack predictions made by Quick Heal Security Labs in 2018 that proved to be true, flagging off the possibility for future cyber-attacks. The report also sheds light on detection highlights of 2018 for both Windows and Android, with a breakup of detections made per day, per hour, per minute, and the entire year, along with a list of top 10 Windows and Android malware [12].

Fig. 4. Quick Heal statistics

Conclusions

Based on the research results, it can be concluded that the ISO/IEC 27034 standard regulates that vulnerability testing should be carried out, but it is not specified how and what should be tested for vulnerabilities. NIST and NIAP both refer to OWASP MASVS and contain controls by which the mobile application is tested, mainly focusing on vulnerabilities that relate to vulnerabilities in data storage and authorization. This is confirmed by statistics provided by Digital Security. The most recognized is MASVS. One of the parts of MASVS describes what and how to test.

It should be noted that all standards rather weakly assess vulnerabilities that relate to interaction with the API. As it can be seen from the tests described in Section 3.1, the most critical vulnerabilities are vulnerabilities that are associated with interaction with the application server.

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